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Introduction

Inclusive education is the most effective way to give all children a fair chance to go to school, learn and develop the skills they need to thrive. Inclusive education means all children in the same classrooms, in the same school. It means real learning opportunities for groups who have traditionally been excluded not only children with disabilities, but speakers of minority languages too.

Inclusive education for CWSN has been one of the major interventions of the erstwhile Sarva Sikshya Abhiyan (SSA) RTE and RMSA schemes. From the year 2028-19 Samagra Sikshya lays emphasis on improving quality of education for all students including CWSN.

Thus this intervention is an essential component under Samagra Sikshya. The component provides support for various student oriental activities which include identification and assessment of CWSN, provision of aids and appliances, corrective surgeries, Braille books, large print books and uniforms therapeutic services, development of Teaching Learning Material (TLM), assistive devices and equipments, environment building and orientation programme to create positive attitude and awareness about nature and needs of CSWN, purchase & development of instructional materials, in-service training of special educators and general teachers on curriculum adaptation, stipend for girls with special needs etc. The component also emphasizes the implementation of the Right to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009 for children with special needs (within the age group of 6-14 years). In addition, separate resource support (financial assistance towards salary of special educators) is also made available in order to appropriately address the needs of CWSN within the school.

Inclusive Education Programme

The Department of School Education and Literacy, MHRD was previously implementing Sarva Sikshya Abhiyan as the main programme for Universalizing Elementary Education for all children from 6-14 years of age. SSA has adopted a more expansive and

broad based understating of the concept of inclusion, where in a multi-option model of educating CWSN was being implemented.

The Right to free and compulsory education (RTE Act, 2009) mandates free and compulsory elementary education to all children including CWSN. This act provides legal framework that entitles all children between the ages of 6-14 years free and compulsory admission, attendance and completion of elementary education. Section 3(2) of the RTE Act lays emphasis on the elementary education of children with disabilities has the right to opt for home based education. Presently Samagra Sikshya aims to cover all children with special needs (CWSN) in a continuum from classes I to XII. Under Samagra Sikshya, in the year 2018-19, an out lay of Rs. 1023.50 crore has been approved. Therefore, the total number of special educators and resource persons available to address the specific needs of children with special needs is 27,774.

The objectives of this component are:

- Identification of children with disabilities at the school level and assessment of their educational needs.
- Provision of aids and appliances, assistive devices, to the children with special needs as per requirement.
- Removal of architectural barriers in schools so that CWSN have access to classrooms, laborites, play/recreational area and toilets in the school.
- Supplying appropriate teaching learning materials, medical facilities, vocational training support, guidance and counseling services, therapeutic services to children with special needs as per his/ her requirement in convergence with departments.
- General school teachers will be sensitized and trained to teach and involve children with special needs in general classroom.
- For existing special educators, capacity building programmes will be undertaken.
- CWSN will have asses to support service through special educators, establishment of resource rooms, vocational education, therapeutic service and counseling etc.

From Perspective of Convergence

The appropriate Govt. and local authorities such as Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Department of Empowerment of Persons with Disability, Public Works Department (PWD), Ministry of Rural Development, Ministry of Skill Development, Ministry of Sports and Health and Family Welfare, Ministry of Women and Child Development etc. shall endeavor that all educational institution funded or recognized by them provide inclusive education to the children with disabilities and towards that end shall:

- Admit them without discrimination and provided education and opportunities for sports and recreation activities equally with others.
- Make building campus and various facilities accessible.
- Provide reasonable accommodation according to the individuals requirements.
- Providing necessary support individualized or otherwise in environment that maximizes academic and social development consistent with the goal of full inclusion.
- Ensure that the education to persons who are blind or deaf or both is imparted in the most appropriate languages and modes and means of communication.
- Detect specific learning disabilities in children at the earliest and take suitable pedagogical and other measures to overcome them.
- Monitor participation, progress in terms of attainment levels and completion of education in respect of every student with disability.
- Provide transportation facilities to the children with disabilities having high support needs.

Provisions for CWSN Included Under Samagra Sikshya

- Support has been enhanced from Rs. 3000/- per child per annum to Rs. 3500/- per child per annum.
- Stipend for girls with special needs has been expanded from the previous allocation to girls from Classes IX to XII (RMSA), to classes I to XII (Samagra Sikshya) in order to encourage girls for enrollment and retention and complete their schooling, stipend is provided through direct benefit transfer.

- The provision for home based education covering children with several multiple disabilities has been extended for children till class XII under the Samagra Sikshya Scheme. In the year 2018-19, the provision for home based education covered 43,996 children with severe / multiple disabilities with an outlay of Rs. 9.22 Crore.
- Allocation for resource support through special educators has been made separately in order to appropriately address the learning needs of CSEN from elementary to senior secondary level.
- The financial support for salary for existing and new special educators (as per the Samagra Sikshya norm for salary of teacher). This allocation is over and above the norm of Rs.3500/- towards student oriented component.

Importance of Inclusive Education for the Children with Special Needs

Education for the children with special needs in India is quite a debatable topic. Through we have the presence of special schools, the numbers are far less than what we need. But it's also a fact that inclusive education is the right way of inculcating skills among special needs children. The acceptance of disabled children is more efficient when there is a presence of inclusive education. Most schools in India understand this aspect.

Inclusive education is not only about education together. It is a way of life where special needs children learn to grow with developing children.

Over, the years, the benefits of providing inclusive education to all children have been shown. Inclusive education is very important because.

- All children can be part of their community and develop a sense of belongingness and become better prepared for life in the community as children and adults.
- It provides better opportunities for learning children with varying abilities are often better motivated when they learn in classes surrounded by other children.
- It allows children to work on individual goals while being with other students of their age.
- It encourages the involvement of parents in the education of their children and the activities of their local schools.

- It fosters a culture of respect and belonging. It also provides the opportunity to learn about and accept individual differences.

Conclusion

Inclusive education is not just for some children. Inclusive education is a way of thinking about how to be creative to make our schools a place where all children can participate. As a value, inclusive education reflects the expectation that we want all of our children to be appreciated and accepted throughout life.

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